

NOVEL ECO-FRIENDLY MgO-BASED AGGREGATES: THE ROAD FROM CONCEPT TO PILOT-SCALE

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ABSTRACT

This work applied the fundamentals of microstructure development and pilot-scale validations to propose novel eco-friendly aggregates, inspired by magnesia-chromium compositions. Initial evaluations revealed that the latter comprises a periclase matrix with embedded spinel precipitates, which induces self-microcracking due to thermal expansion mismatch, resulting in a flexible microstructure. Computational tools were, then, applied to find non-toxic alternative systems. Out of 154 evaluated compositions, four were produced at laboratory scale. Advanced characterization techniques (e.g. EBSD and Synchrotron XRD) were applied to analyse the influence of lattice parameter misfit on the morphology of spinel precipitates. The findings pointed out that the morphology of spinel can be tailored through minor chemical changes. Furthermore, one of these compositions was scaled up to pilot production and tested as refractory aggregate. The promising attained results are presented and discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

To meet the demands of steelmaking processes, electrofused magnesia-chromite refractories (AMCE) have been broadly used since the 1960s [1]. These materials, classified as compositionally complex ceramics [2], are mainly comprised of periclase and a spinel solid solution derived from the combination of different spinel structures (AB_2O_4 phases, where A represents a divalent cation and B a trivalent one) [3]. However, despite their high resistance to corrosion and thermal shock damage, AMCE have received little attention from the scientific community in recent decades due to its toxicity, resulting from the formation of hexavalent chromium during disposal [4].

Therefore, there is still a gap in understanding the mechanisms that impart the properties of AMCE, and the compositionally complex design approach [5] could be used to formulate non-toxic substitutes with competitive costs and performance. Nevertheless, although this novel strategy paves a broad path for developing innovative materials, the huge number of possible formulations makes the selection via trial and error unfeasible, demanding the use of computational tools and assertive experimental validation [6]. Thus, this study employed multiple techniques to assess the mechanisms underlying the properties of AMCE and, based on the findings, concepts of complex composition ceramics were applied to identify ecological alternatives to AMCE. From the 154 systems virtually analyzed, four were electrofused in a lab-scale arc melter, whereas one was selected for pilot-scale trials.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The microstructural characterization initially focused on commercially available electrofused magnesia-chrome aggregates (Chenglong, China). As-received samples were evaluated by scanning electron microscopy (BSE, EDS and EBSD), carried out in a MIRA instrument (Tescan, Czech Republic). The chemical and mineralogical compositions of the EMCA samples were analyzed using X-ray fluorescence (MagiX PRO, Malvern Panalytical, UK) and X-ray diffraction (beamline ID11, European Synchrotron Radiation Facility, France). Thermodynamic calculations were carried out using FactSage software (version 8.3, CRCT, Canada). Additionally, thermal expansion coefficient mismatches in these systems were analyzed via computational calculations using Python codes hosted and run on Google Colab.

To find environmental-friendly alternatives to chromium-containing materials, the same thermodynamic approach was employed to evaluate the solidification path of binary, ternary, or quaternary spinel systems along with 66.4% by weight of MgO, resulting in 154 distinct formulations. The three most promising systems were experimentally processed in a lab-scale arc furnace (MAM-1, Edmund Buehler, Germany) using the raw materials described in Table 1. These samples had their microstructure evaluated using scanning electron microscopy, XRF and XRD (as specified above). Due to its promising results, a pilot scale production (batch of 300 Kg) of Comp.1 via pressureless sintering (1760 °C) was carried out at RHI Magnesita facilities. The resulting material was used to replace the coarse EMCA fraction (0.6 mm – 4.75 mm) in a refractory brick formulation, giving rise to Brick_Comp.1. Its apparent porosity (immersion test with kerosene, ASTM C20-00), elastic modulus (following ASTM C597-22), thermal shock damage resistance ($\Delta T = 1000$ °C, following ASTM C1525), modulus of rupture at room temperature and 1485 °C (Kratos K500/2000 equipment, Brazil) and corrosion resistance (dynamic test at 1700 °C for 5 h, using low-carbon steel and fayalitic slag as corrosion media) were assessed and compared to the commercial reference (Brick_EMCA).

Table 1: Compositions and raw materials used in the production of electrofused samples.

Raw material	FMC R 18-20	MgO	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	Ni ₂ O ₃
Supplier	Liaoyang Chenglong, China	RHI Magnesita, Austria		Fermag, Brazil	Almatis, Germany	Metalloys, Brazil
Id	wt%					
EMCA*	100	-	-	-	-	-
Comp.1	-	69.5	5.6	24.9	-	-
Comp.2	-	66.4	11.3	8.4	5.3	8.6
Comp.3	-	71.1	4.2	18.7	6.0	-

* Chemical analysis by XRF pointed out MgO (66.6 wt%), Cr₂O₃ (18.3 wt%), Fe₂O₃ (7.2 wt%) and Al₂O₃ (6.5 wt%) as the main compounds.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Firstly, the microstructure of the commercial EMCA was analyzed by SEM/EDS as shown in Figure 1 (a). In agreement with the literature, a highly microcracked structure containing distinct regions was observed, which is responsible for the good flexibility of these aggregates and provides their high thermal shock damage resistance. The EDS data, together with XRD – see Figure 1 (b) –, highlighted that the aggregate is formed by 66 wt% of a periclase (MgO, green color in the micrograph) matrix containing 34 wt% of nodular spinel precipitates (purple). Although the microstructure of EMCA has already been reported, the mechanism that leads to its cracking behavior was not. Thus, microcrack generation due to thermal expansion mismatch between the distinct phases during the cooling process was considered. By applying the model developed by Lucchini et al. [7], it could be concluded that the MgO matrix will stay under tensile stress during the cooling of the aggregate, as its thermal expansion coefficient is higher than that estimated for the complex spinel ($15.8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ and $\alpha = 9.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$). This model also indicates that spinel precipitates bigger than $3 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ – the case of EMCA, in which precipitate size is $15 \pm 2 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ – will induce matrix microcracking. These cracks, in turn, will propagate preferentially oriented in the $\{110\}$ family of the crystallographic plane of the matrix, resulting from the Zener-Stroh cracking mechanism [8].

Figure 1: (a) SEM/EDS image and (b) synchrotron X-ray diffractogram from commercial EMCA samples, adapted from [3] and [9], respectively.

Although the origin of the microcracking pattern seen in EMCA was now clear, the reasons for the formation of a matrix-precipitate morphology remained obscure. In this sense, thermodynamic calculations were carried out to assess the solidification profile of this material, as presented in Figure 2. This solidification diagram pointed out that chromium plays a key role in this system, enabling the formation of a MgO solid solution at high temperatures, which exsolves spinel precipitates as the material cools down.

Figure 2: EMCA solidification path assessed by thermodynamic calculations carried out in FactSage 8.2 software and using the chemical composition evaluated by X-ray fluorescence, adapted from [3].

The results discussed so far pointed out the mechanism and key features responsible for the formation of the EMCA microstructure and, consequently, good thermomechanical properties. In summary, a system capable of forming a broad solid solution with MgO at high temperature, but exsolving a second phase presenting a lower thermal expansion coefficient as internal precipitates and mean particle size higher than the critical value to induce fracture by thermal expansion mismatch is required to trigger the Zener-Stroh cracking mechanism, leading to highly oriented microcrack formation. This intricate set of features explains why finding other compositions to replace the EMCA is so difficult, especially using the traditional selection paradigm. Therefore, the compositionally complex ceramic (CCC) selection approach was used to assess promising alternatives that could mimetize the microstructure of EMCA but without containing chromium addition. Using thermodynamic calculations, systems containing binary, ternary, or quaternary equimolar spinel phases together with 66.4 wt% of periclase had their mineralogical composition tracked down from 2800 °C to room temperature. This approach pointed out three promising systems (compositions depicted in Table 1), which were experimentally produced in a lab-scale arc melter. A video of the electrofusion process can be seen by clicking on [this link](#).

The mineralogical and morphological features of all electrofused specimens (EMCA and Comp.1-3) were, then, assessed by synchrotron-based XRD (not presented here, but

available in [9]) and their respective EBSD (see Figure 3). As targeted, both analyses showed that all samples were comprised of similar amounts of periclase (66 wt%) and spinel (34 wt%). Nevertheless, clear differences in the morphologies and sizes of the obtained spinel were observed, with the EMCA sample showing the largest average precipitate size, whereas Comp. 1 was the only one to present non-spherical precipitates.

Figure 3: EBSD images showing phase identification and orientation (inverse pole figure, IPF), both superimposed to the image quality (IQ), adapted from [9].

However, the main outcome of the EBSD technique is the crystallographic orientation of the different phases. Analyzing the orientation maps, one can notice that the spinel precipitates were formed in the same crystallographic orientation as the periclase matrix for all samples. Nonetheless, the question that arises after analyzing such results is: if all compositions exhibited similar behavior regarding the crystallographic orientation between precipitates and the matrix, what then accounts for the differences observed in the morphology of the spinels formed in each of them? A deeper look into these systems pointed out that the precipitate morphology is highly dependent on the similarity – or lack of that – between the spinel and periclase lattice parameters. Supported by the synchrotron XRD, it could be seen that the higher the misfit between the lattice parameters, the bigger and more spherical the precipitates, though kinetic aspects could not be neglected. This behavior is explained by the higher energy of dissimilar interfaces, which generates a driving force to minimize such regions by creating bigger and spherical precipitates [9].

Conversely, for Comp.1 – in which the higher lattice parameter compatibility resulted in coherent interfaces –, the spinel can grow forming a 3D network, as highlighted in Figure 4 (a), which shows images from Comp. 1 after selective etching of the periclase matrix. The understanding of this mechanism enables the microstructural tailoring, as demonstrated by a small Nb_2O_5 addition (3 wt%) into Comp.1, which increased the lattice misfit, changing the precipitate morphology.

Figure 4: SE images highlighting the spinel morphology of (a-b) the etched surface of Comp.1, and (c-d) Comp.1 processed with the addition of 3 wt% of Nb₂O₅, adapted from [9].

Nevertheless, when it comes to their use as eco-friendly alternatives to EMCA raw material in refractory applications, it is not yet entirely clear what is the optimized spinel morphology. On one hand, spherical precipitates with a diameter greater than 3 μm will increase the formation of microcracks in the MgO matrix [3], leading to higher flexibility and, consequently, improving the thermal shock damage resistance. On the other, the formation of a 3D network of refined precipitates, as observed for Comp. 1, can result in an aggregate with higher work of fracture and corrosion resistance due to the interaction of cracks with such structures and the more uniform distribution of the spinel phase, respectively.

Aiming at collecting more information to support the selection of the most suitable composition to be tested in a pilot scale, the specimens had their dilatometric profile assessed up to 1400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, as presented in Figure 5 (a-d). Additionally, to enable further interpretations, the physical thermal expansion coefficient (α) and the phase profile under equilibrium conditions were calculated. Initially, analyzing the results obtained for the reference sample (EMCA), no significant α changes were detected, remaining at a value close to $15 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$. Such monotonic behavior was expected because no major changes in the phase profile are predicted up to 1400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Conversely, all other sintered compositions displayed non-monotonic changes in their α -value at elevated temperatures ($> 1200 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), being Comp.1 the most notable case, as its α -value peaked at $90 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$ during cooling. The comparison between the dilatometric profile and the mineralogical composition calculated by computational thermodynamics pointed out that this α change is assigned to the dissolution/precipitation of spinel in the periclase phase. In this sense, the narrow α peak generated during the cooling of Comp.1 is assigned to the favored spinel precipitation kinetics due to the high lattice compatibility between the spinel and MgO phases.

Figure 5: Dilatometric profile, thermal expansion coefficient and phase content up to 1400 °C, adapted from [10].

But if these dilatometric changes are, in fact, related to spinel solution/precipitation, they should be reversible with temperature. To evaluate this hypothesis, Comp.1 was thermally cycled up to 1400 °C five times and its thermal expansion coefficient during this procedure can be seen in Figure 6 (a). Despite small variations in the α peaks during the first two cooling cycles (likely due to the thermal history of the specimen), its behavior was reversible and highly reproducible, attesting to the hypothesis that it arises from the mineralogical changes occurring in the sample. Nevertheless, the high α -values detected during the cooling of Comp.1-sint. could raise concerns about its negative effect on the thermal shock damage performance of materials produced with this formulation, as it could lead to higher tensile stresses on the material's surface for the same temperature change (ΔT) during cooling, increasing the likelihood of nucleation and crack growth.

However, as this non-linear behavior takes place at high temperatures (~ 1250 °C), in which periclase (the matrix) exhibits a greater ability to accommodate stresses without cracking, this peak for the α -value should not result in appreciable losses of mechanical strength of the aggregates. The elastic modulus of Comp.1 samples was sequentially evaluated after five heating and cooling cycles at 1400 °C and the obtained values can be seen in Figure 6 (b). The small variations in the elastic modulus corroborate the previous discussions. Therefore, after attesting the feasibility of using Comp. 1 as a refractory raw material and considering its distinctive microstructural features (3D arranged spinel precipitates), this composition was selected for the initial pilot trials.

Figure 6: Linear thermal expansion coefficient (a) and elastic modulus (b) of Comp.1 after subsequent thermal cycles up to 1400 °C, adapted from [10].

A batch of 300 kilograms of briquettes from Comp. 1 was produced via conventional sintering at 1760 $^\circ\text{C}$, using RHI Magnesita facilities. The phase content, total porosity and microstructure of the resulting material were evaluated (results not presented here) and compared to those of the electrofused samples. Whereas the morphology and quantity of spinel precipitates remained consistent regardless of the production techniques, the sintered briquettes exhibited significantly higher total porosity ($\sim 10 \text{ vol}\%$) compared with the electrofused Comp.1 or the commercial EMCA ($\sim 3 \text{ vol}\%$ for both). This higher porosity should be taken into account when comparing the properties of bricks produced with the sintered raw material (Brick_Comp.1) and the reference one (Brick_EMCA). After this characterization, the sintered briquettes were grounded and sieved into different granulometries, which were used to replace the coarse fraction (0.6 mm – 4.75 mm) of EMCA in Brick_Comp.1. After pressing, both Brick_Comp.1 and Brick_EMCA were fired at 1760 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 8 h and characterized by some physical properties, as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Apparent porosity, modulus of rupture (MOR), elastic modulus (E) after sintering and the residual E after 5 thermal shock cycles at different temperatures.

Properties	Apparent porosity (vol%)	MOR (MPa)	MOR at 1485 $^\circ\text{C}$ (MPa)	E after sintering (GPa)	Residual E - 5 cycles at 700 $^\circ\text{C}$	Residual E - 5 cycles at 1200 $^\circ\text{C}$
Brick_EMCA	11.1 ± 0.4	13 ± 1	5.5 ± 0.4	93 ± 10	$43 \pm 5 \%$	$4 \pm 1 \%$
Brick_Comp.1	13.5 ± 0.2	11 ± 3	4.3 ± 0.1	73 ± 10	$33 \pm 4 \%$	$8 \pm 1 \%$

The higher porosity of the aggregates in Comp.1 led to the greater apparent porosity observed in the compositions that incorporated this raw material when compared with Brick_EMCA. As a result, Brick_Comp.1 presented a lower elastic modulus after both sintering and thermal shock at 700 $^\circ\text{C}$, as well as reduced modulus of rupture at room temperature and high temperature. The retained elastic modulus after 5 thermal cycles at 1200 $^\circ\text{C}$ was, in turn, slightly higher. Despite these differences, they were relatively small, especially when considering the uncertainties associated with the measurements and the

fact that an electrofused raw material (EMCA) was compared to a sintered one. In addition to the characterizations described earlier, the corrosion resistance of both samples was evaluated at 1700 °C for 5 h, using low-carbon steel and fayalitic slag as the corrosion media. Figure 7 (a) shows the bricks before testing, whereas Figure 7 (b) presents the wear on the metal and slag lines. The corrosion test also revealed a similar trend, where Brick_Comp.1 performed slightly worse than the reference one. However, the difference was, again, slight and likely attributed to the higher porosity and small crystal size of the sintered Comp.1 compared to EMCA.

Figure 7: images of the bricks after the dynamic corrosion test (a) and the measured wear (b).

The most significant outcome of these pilot trials was that the synthetic aggregates produced by the compositionally complex design approach were suitable for partially replacing EMCA in refractory applications. The next steps in this research will involve carrying out a pilot scale electrofusion process for Comp.1 to allow for a fairer comparison with the commercial EMCA, as well as evaluating bricks made from the other synthetic compositions (Comp. 2 and 3). Thus, the insights gained from the pilot trials can be integrated into the materials selection algorithm, paving the way for the design of optimized compositions tailored to specific applications.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The mechanism behind the good thermal shock resistance of commercially available EMCA was investigated using multiple techniques and the findings were applied to support a computational thermodynamic selection method based on the compositionally complex design approach. From the 154 chromium-free systems evaluated, three of the most promising candidates were produced in a lab-scale arc melter. Although the eco-friendly compositions exhibited a similar microstructure to EMCA (periclase matrix with spinel precipitates), their precipitate morphology varied, with Comp. 2 and 3 displaying sphere-like shapes and Comp. 1 presenting spinel forming a 3D network. The differences in morphology were explored through EBSD and synchrotron XRD, highlighting the role of lattice parameter

misfit. Additionally, dilatometric profiles were assessed up to 1400 °C, showing that spinel dissolution and precipitation affected the specimens' dimensional stability, but did not spoil the elastic modulus after thermal cycling. Due to its promising features, Comp. 1 was selected for pilot trials. A 300-kilogram batch of briquettes from this composition was produced via conventional sintering and used to replace the coarse fraction of EMCA in a commercial refractory brick. Although the brick containing the Chromium-free aggregates performed slightly worse than the reference, this was likely due to the higher porosity of the sintered aggregate. The main outcome of the pilot trial was demonstrating the feasibility of using the chromium-free aggregate in refractory products. However, a pilot-scale electrofusion of Comp. 1 will be essential for a fair comparison with commercial EMCA.

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Se otorga el presente certificado a

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